

Impacts of Green Practices on Customer Satisfaction among Selected Coffee Shops in Dasmariñas City, Cavite

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Abstract: This research is focused on the effects of green practices and customer satisfaction among selected coffee shops in Dasmariñas City, Cavite. The researchers include measures of demographics that drive their respondents and their views on how green practices affect customers' satisfaction. Drawing on the input-process-output (IPO) model and the Customer Satisfaction Model, this study aims to understand the relationship results showing that green practices may be causally linked to customer satisfaction. A descriptive-quantitative approach is used, and thereby 150 respondents' data were analyzed. All the studies give positive findings regarding the satisfaction component of "green practices," which are respectable as significant correlations that green practices have with elements Customer Satisfaction such as quality for products, service, usage of energy efficient appliances, presentation packing/ packaging in addition to cleanliness and reputation/image. The conducted research offers some insight in terms of pragmatic recommendations on how a coffee shop can manage customers' expectations through green management. This study provides practical recommendations on green business practices and consumer perspectives about sustainability, creating a brighter future with respect to sustainability issues related to the coffee industry as well as society more generally.

Keywords: Green practices, customer satisfaction, coffee shops, sustainability, demographic profile, environmental awareness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Everyone in the world should be concerned about the environment, and no matter where they come from, all governments, businesses, and individuals should make climate change mitigation their top priority. Individuals all over the world are working hard to embrace green practices and protect the environment, even if some people are more serious about saving the planet than others. The diversity of cultures and climates provides unique opportunities for environmental protection.

The natural environment is a beautiful destination that can be offered to guests; it is the source of the food consumed in restaurants; as well as the air and water that customers breathe and drink; Going green increases word-of-mouth marketing, customer loyalty, and customer satisfaction. These realities serve as justification for becoming more involved and active in environmental protection.

The United Nations (UN) established Sustainable Development Goal 13 (UN SDG13), which is about climate action, to address the issue of environmental protection on a global scale. It is one of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals that the United Nations General Assembly established in 2015. The official mission statement for this goal is to "take immediate action against climate change and its impacts." The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the leading environmental authority in the United Nations system, uses its expertise to strengthen environmental standards and practices while assisting in the implementation of environmental obligations at the country, regional, and global levels.

The Philippines, like other countries, has seen an increase in the number of people concerned about environmental issues. That is why, the UN SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals), which are global initiative to put an end to poverty, safeguard the environment and climate, and guarantee that everyone may live in peace and prosperity are being implemented in the country by the Philippine government.

Additionally, the Philippine government developed six major laws on green practices and environmental protection. These are (1) PD1586: Environmental Impact Assessment Law; (2) RA6969: Toxic Substances & Hazardous Waste Management Act; (3) RA8749: The Clean Air Act of 1999; (4) RA9003: Ecological Solid Waste Management Act; (5) RA9275: Clean Water Act; and (6) RA9512: The Environmental Awareness & Education Act of 2009.

Specifically, the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act (Aquino et al., 2022), aims to address the Philippines' garbage disposal issues. This law establishes logical and ecological solid waste disposal, transportation, segregation, and storage rules that ensure community health and proper solid waste disposal, transportation, segregation, and storage. 3 R's (Reduce, Reuse, and Recycling) the program is promoted. Reduces the nation's waste (Aquino et al., 2013).

In our present times, it has become especially important for companies, organizations, and business establishments to face these environmental issues and concerns since customers are becoming increasingly concerned about environmental protection. Going green may help one's business to save money on energy and food and become more appealing to customers. While making one's company more environmentally friendly may appear to be a daunting task, there are numerous simple changes that restaurants and other food service businesses can implement to reduce their negative environmental impacts. Moreover, implementing green initiatives can help a business contribute to environmental protection as well as achieve outstanding reputation among its customers.

With the growing awareness and implementation of green practices among food service businesses, particularly coffee shops, the researchers opted to conduct this research to determine how green practices affect customer satisfaction. The researchers aim to gather information about customers' demographic profile as well as their perceptions of the positive and negative impacts of green practices on customer satisfaction when they dine at the selected coffee shops.

Furthermore, the results of this study will also advance knowledge of and give a deeper understanding of how these green practices affect customer satisfaction, which will be advantageous to future researchers, coffee shop owners, and the beverage service sector. The results of this study may also give coffee shop owners new insights into how to raise customer satisfaction by more effectively integrating green practices into their daily operations.

Research Paradigm

Maykut and Moorehouse (1994) state "a paradigm is a collection of fundamental beliefs about how reality works that are tied to one another. Any paradigm is based on a set of assumptions about how reality works. Although the paradigm itself cannot be tested, it serves as the foundation around which we construct our verifiable knowledge."

The researchers will use the input-process-output (IPO) model. The input-process-output (IPO) model will be used by researchers. The IPO model has a causal structure, with output resulting from a customer comparing their experiences to their expectations. This functional graph illustrates the variables utilized and the methodology of the study to help the reader comprehend it. The respondents' demographic information as well as their evaluation of how using green practices affects customer satisfaction are inputs. The procedure entails the use of a self-made survey questionnaire as the data collection tool, as well as statistical processing and analysis of all data gathered. In terms of output, the researchers will develop recommendations based on the study's findings and will propose a set of enhanced guidelines on green practices that will improve customer satisfaction even further.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored from the Customer Satisfaction Model of Zeithaml Bitner (2012). Customer satisfaction is the feeling of someone who is satisfied or dissatisfied with a product or service after comparing reality and expectations (Kotler, 2012). According to Zeithaml and Bitner (2012), satisfaction is not only a much broader concept than simply assessing service quality, but it is also influencing other factors. According to their Customer Satisfaction Model, customer's perception of service quality, product quality, price, as well as situational and personal factors are influencing customer satisfaction.

On the other hand, customer dissatisfaction occurs when performance is below expectations, whereas customer satisfaction occurs when performance meets expectations (Kotler & Keller, 2003).

Statement of the Problem

The main objective of this study is to assess the impacts of green practices on customer satisfaction among selected coffee shops in Dasmariñas City, Cavite.

Specifically, this study aims to provide an answer to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

1.1 Age;

1.2 Gender;

1.3 Civil Status;

1.4 Educational Attainment;

1.5 Employment Status;

1.6 Budget Allotment Per Visit in

Coffee Shop;

1.7 Frequency of Visit in Coffee Shop

2. What are the impacts of green practices on customer satisfaction among selected coffee shops in Dasmarinas City, Cavite in terms of:
 - 2.1 Product Quality
 - 2.2 Service Quality
 - 2.3 Use of Energy efficient Appliances.
 - 2.4 Packaging/Presentation
 - 2.5 Cleanliness & Sanitation
 - 2.6 Image & Reputation
3. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their assessment of the impacts of green practices on customer satisfaction?
4. Based on the findings, what enhanced guidelines on green practices can be proposed to the selected coffee shops in Dasmarinas City, Cavite?

Statement of Hypothesis

The null hypothesis in this study is stated as follows: There is no significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their assessment of the effects of green practices on customer satisfaction in selected coffee shops in Dasmarinas City, Cavite.

The alternative hypothesis is as follows: There is a strong correlation between the demographic profile of the respondents and their assessment of the impacts of green practices on customer satisfaction in selected coffee shops in Dasmarinas City, Cavite.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Global Environmental Awareness

Environmental awareness is increasingly not only a common interest but also a significant topic in academic research. Environmental awareness is the result of people's understanding of ecological issues as well as their capacity to take these issues into account and evaluate how they might impact the environment and the community (Alamsyah, Othman & Mohammed2020). Environmental awareness, according to recent studies, has a significant impact on a customer's purchase intent (Xu, Wang, Yu, 2020). Environmental awareness is necessary for the green practice to be integrated into human actions. For people to comprehend the significance of environmental consciousness to save the earth and live in harmony with other species, awareness does not develop on its own; rather, it needs to be encouraged (Tam, 2016 and Omoogun et al., 2016).

Scholars in food service, hospitality, and tourism have been studying environmental concerns and consumer behavior. (De Groeve & Bleys, 2017; Gupta et al., 2019; Han et al., 2018; Huang & Liu, 2017; Kim & Yun, 2019). For instance, environmental concern drives pro-environmental behaviors and intents like attending "green" coffee shops since it increases knowledge of environmental effects (Kim & Yun, 2019). As customers become more conscious of deterioration, growing pollution, global warming, and the depletion of natural resources, their interest in environmental protection and green activities has grown. (Yadav, Khandelwal, & Tripathi, 2017)

Green Practices

The primary goal of green and sustainable practices is to increase productivity while decreasing waste (Korhonen et al., 2018). Green and sustainable production improves the firm's operational performance by maximizing product and material functionality while ensuring efficient resource consumption (Sehnm et al., 2019). Due to this phenomenon, a rising number of hotels are implementing green practices into their daily operations to lessen their impact on the environment (Martnez Garca de Leaniz et al., 2018; Verma & Chandra, 2018).

Green practices are getting popular as they provide a sustainable supply chain, which gives companies an edge over competitors in the market (Zailani, et al., 2012). The implementation of green manufacturing processes is widespread, according to Scur and Barbosa (2017), and there is a high degree of environmental and social performance, including proper adherence to environmental policy. Businesses are introducing green practices to compete and gain market share, which will boost sales Yildiz and Sezen (2019). Green practices have an impact on the company's sustainability performance in

terms of profitability and, eventually, achieving a competitive edge in the market. These practices include a decrease in price or cost, an improvement in quality and service, and a decrease in waste disposal (Yildiz & Sezen, 2019).

Use of energy efficient appliances

Reducing energy use and improving energy efficiency are two aspects of energy sustainability. Eco-friendly appliances can lessen the annual emissions of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. You can lessen your carbon footprint and contribution to climate change by upgrading your appliances in Coffee Shops Sustainable energy consumption entails purchasing products that use less energy, cost less, and are more energy efficient. Using energy-efficient household appliances (EEHA) entails not only reducing energy waste in general but also making use of environmentally friendly energy sources within the home. Some coffee makers come with a "energy saving mode" or "eco-mode" that can be implemented into the menu. After a specific amount of time, this mode reduces the heating element's temperature, time (e.g. 5 minutes) (e.g. 5 minutes). By conserving energy resources, energy-saving appliances aid in the growth of low-carbon economies. Consumption of energy, goods, and services can significantly increase a household's GHG (greenhouse gas) emissions. It is considered sustainable or green consumption to buy products that use less energy and have less of an impact on the environment. Products that save energy for consumers includes:

1. Air conditioning appliances such as heaters, fans, humidifiers
2. White goods (major household electrical appliances such as air conditioners, refrigeration, water heater etc.
3. Small appliances (kitchen appliances such as ovens, electric kettles, coffee machines)

Customer Satisfaction

Current green practices influenced customer satisfaction. The analysis results offer a solution to the second issue, which is how existing green practices impact customer satisfaction. This study's findings are consistent with those of Singjai, Winata, and Kummer's research (2018). Businesses understand that considering customer needs is essential for the design and delivery of products and services, regardless of how advanced their technology capabilities may be. Most companies that have been successful have done so by putting their customers' needs first (Esmaeli et al., 2019). As a result, identifying customer needs and exceeding their expectations is critical for every business. Satisfaction is a reaction to interactions that meet expectations (Demira and Durmaz, 2020: 99). Hsiao et al. (2018) discovered that understanding what is important for a company's survival in current green practices is necessary to provide the best results and satisfy customers who come. Customers who are pleased with current green practices will be more loyal.

Customer Environmental Awareness

Environmental issues are a major source of worry for most countries. The preservation of the environment is an activity that is essential to the food business because generate more trash, consume a lot more use natural resources, save energy, and both goods and services.

People are now choosing and embracing a greener lifestyle as they become more ecologically conscious. Local government units (LGUs) are redesigning their cities to make them more livable and conducive to a healthy population.

Since greater environmental concern is linked to better levels of perceived quality, satisfaction, and loyalty, environmental concern has become more crucial in determining customer satisfaction (Wu & Cheng, 2017). In the hospitality industry, the level of customer environmental concern is important, as is customer behavior, which has environmental consequences (Okumus, Köseoglu, Chan, Hon, & Avci, 2019). As customers' attitudes toward environmental concerns change, environmental concern is one of the most significant indicators of diners' pro-environmental action (Shin et al., 2017a). Customers who value the environment are more likely to pay more and choose eco-friendly establishments (Shin, Im, Jung, & Severt, 2019). As a result, customers who care more about the environment are more inclined to frequent restaurants that use eco-friendly procedures than their rivals (Joo et al., 2018; Shin et al., 2017a, 2018, 2019).

Coffee Shops

Customers are more likely to spend time with their friends and family at their favorite coffee shop. Some coffee shops offer their customers a work environment. According to the vice-president of the Asian Coffee Federation and the president of the Thai Barista Association, coffee is a rising star in the food and beverage business, with sales predicted to treble in the next five years (Jitpleecheep & Hicks, 2019). During the COVID-19 outbreak in 2020–2021, reduced demand, lockdown, and social stratification regulations had a detrimental effect on the food service industry, including coffee shops (Euromonitor, 2021).

Businesses that offer similar services face fierce competition in a competitive industry. Coffee shops, for example, strive hard to create innovative tactics that will provide businesses with a competitive edge and retain customers. The domestic coffee market and consumption in Thailand have increased in recent years, with the total coffee market estimated to be 25.8 billion baht in 2019. Thailand SMEs Center, 2020. Coffee shops and cafés are two types of coffee service businesses (Food Intelligence Center Thailand, 2015). According to Euromonitor, there were 8025 coffee shops in Thailand in 2018. (Jitpleecheep & Hicks, 2019). Demand is still increasing even though the average annual coffee consumption in Thailand is only about 300 cups, compared to 600 cups in Europe and 400 cups in Japan (Jitpleecheep & Hicks, 2019). The market is expected to grow at a 7.4 percent annual rate between 2019 and 2023. (Ferris, 2021). The current coffee lifestyle trend is one of the reasons.

The COVID-19 pandemic, combined with increased global awareness of environmental protection, has heightened public concern. Customers are prepared to pay more for things that appear to aid in environmental protection. Alternative tourism and ecotourism are becoming increasingly popular. Coffee production contributes significantly to hazardous emissions, non-biodegradable waste, and deforestation. From a sustainability perspective, looking for coffee from ecologically conscientious producers is an excellent way to start. (Boksanski, M., 2022) Coffee that is organically certified. There are several choices for coffee establishments, looking to eliminate or decrease single-use plastic. Without losing quality, a coffee business can lessen its carbon footprint by using paper straws, wooden stirrers, and biodegradable cups and lids. When selecting suppliers, look for companies that are forward-thinking and prioritize environmental safety. (J. Helmer, 2020)

The implementation of environmentally friendly practices, such as utilizing wooden stirrers rather than plastic ones, recyclable take-out containers, or even having a compost pile for organic waste, can help a coffee shop or café become sustainable. This is also true for the origins and processing of their products, which are mostly coffee beans. Coffee beans are considered sustainable when they are sourced in an environmentally and socially responsible manner. (B. Davis, 2020)

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The Descriptive-Quantitative method will be used by the researchers to assess the impact of green practices on customer satisfaction in selected coffee shops in Dasmarias City, Cavite. The quantitative method emphasizes the goals and statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data gathered through polls, questionnaires, and surveys (Creswell, J.W., and Creswell, J.D., 2017). Descriptive research entails gathering data that describes events and then organizing, tabulating, depicting, and describing the data. A survey questionnaire will be used as the data collection instrument in this study. Furthermore, a descriptive-quantitative method is appropriate for this study because the researchers will interpret the data results of the respondents' demographic profile as well as describe the impacts of green practices on customer satisfaction.

Research Locale

The study will be conducted in selected coffee shops in Dasmariñas City, Cavite. The researchers have chosen this location since there are many coffee shops within the locality who are implementing green practices in their operations. Specifically, three selected coffee shops located within Dasmariñas City that will be coded as Coffee Shop A: Starbucks; Coffee Shop B: Coffee Bean & Tea Leaf; and Coffee Shop C: The Coffee Project.

Participants of the Study and Research Sampling

The probability sampling technique will be used by the researchers to identify a representative sample from which to collect data. Because of its ease of use and accurate representation of the larger group, the simple random sampling method will be used to select the sample from the large population. In this method, every member of the population has an equal chance of being selected. The researchers will include 50 customers per coffee shop in the sample size to ensure that each store is represented equally. Because three coffee shops have been chosen, a total of 150 people will take part in the study. Customers who have dined at any of the selected coffee shops are among those who have responded.

Probability Sampling will be useful on this study as it allows researchers to create a sample that is accurately representative of the real-life population of interest.

It is used to improve validity. With probability sampling, statistics are produced from a larger number of randomly chosen units to accurately reflect the entire population.

Research Instrument & Data Gathering Procedures

To collect the data needed to complete the research, the researchers will create a survey questionnaire that will be used as the data collection instrument. The survey questionnaire will be posted online and answered by respondents via Google Form after being validated and approved by the thesis adviser, panel members, and statistician. This is due to the pandemic situation, which only allows for a limited number of face-to-face interactions with respondents.

The Researchers will evaluate the representativeness of a survey by balancing its sample demographics to match the demographics of the target population: Age, Gender, Civil Status, Educational Attainment, Employment Status, Budget Allotment Per Visit in Coffee Shop; and Frequency of Visit in Coffee Shop, internet users.

Once the form is made, We will disseminate it by copying the google form link and post it in any social media forms. The Data will be collected after Respondents answered the form. By default, it saves every response to the Responses tab, which displays lists of responses and summary graphs. An individual response view displays the live form and each respondent's results.

Data Treatment and Analysis

The following statistical tools will be used by the researchers as part of the data treatment and analysis:

The average weighted mean will be used to determine the impact of green practices on customer satisfaction as perceived by customers/respondents in the selected coffee shops in Dasmariñas City, Cavite.

The 4-point Likert Scale will be used to interpret the obtained weighted mean:

Scale Descriptive Equivalent

- 4 High Impact
- 3 Moderate Impact
- 2 Low Impact
- 1 No Impact

The Chi-square will be used to determine the significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and the variables in their assessment of the impacts of green practices on customer satisfaction. For testing relationships between categorical variables, the Chi-square statistic is commonly used. The Chi-Square test's null hypothesis states that no relationship exists between the categorical variables in the population, implying that they are independent.

Lastly, to help the management of a select coffee shop understand how their customers view the consequences of green practices on their level of satisfaction, the study's findings and recommendations will be shared with them. They can utilize this information to enhance their offerings and increase customer satisfaction levels.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered in this study. The course of the analysis and interpretation was guided by the problems presented in Chapter 1.

I. Demographic Profile

Table 1: Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18 years old below	26	17.33%
19 – 29 years old	108	72.00%
30 – 40 years old	15	10.00%
41 – 51 years old	1	0.67%
Average		100%

Upon examining the data on table 1 out of 150 respondents, 26 of them are fall below 18 year's old which is 17.33%, 108 of them are fall between the age of 19 to 29 years' old which is 72%, 15 of them are fall between the age of 30 to 40 years' old which is 10%, and 1 of them are on between 41 to 51 year's old which is 0.67% of the respondents

Table 2: Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Gender

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	78	52%
Female	72	48%
Average		100%

Upon examining the data on table 2, 78 respondents are male which is 52% while 72 of them are female which is 48% with the total of 150 respondents.

Table 3: Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	135	90.00%
Married	13	8.67%
Separated	1	0.67%
Widowed	1	0.67%
Average		100%

Table 3 out of 150 respondents shows the Civil Status of each respondent. 135 of them are Single, which is 90%, 13 of them are married representing the 8.67% of the size, 1 of them or 0.67% of the respondents are Separated and 1 of them is widowed, which is 0.67% of the size.

Table 4: Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
High School Graduate	77	51.33%
Associate Degree/Technical Course	16	10.67%
Bachelor's Degree Graduate	45	30.00%
Master's Degree Graduate	4	2.67%
Average		100%

Table 4 out of 150 respondents shows the Educational Attainment of each respondent. 77 of them are High School Graduates, which is 51.333%, 16 of them are Associate Degree/Technical Course earners representing the 10.67% of the size, 45 of them or 30% of the respondents are Bachelor's Degree Graduates and 4 respondents are Master's Degree Graduates which is 2.67% of the size.

Table 5: Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Employment Status

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage
Unemployed	21	14.00%
Employed	28	18.67%
Self-employed / Business Owner	6	4.00%
Student	95	63.33%
Average		100%

Table 5 out of 100 respondents shows the **Employment Status** of each respondent. 21 of them are Unemployed, which is 14%, 28 of them are Employed representing the 18.67% of the size, 6 of them or 4% of the respondents are Self-employed or Business Owners, and 95 of them are Students which is 63.33% of the respondents.

Table 6: Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Budget Allotment

Budget Allotment	Frequency	Percentage
Php 200 and below	52	34.67%
Php 201-300	53	35.33%
Php 301-400	27	18.00%
Php 401-500	6	4.00%
Php 501 and above	12	8.00%
Average		100%

Table 6 out of 150 respondents shows the Budget Allotment of each respondent. 52 of them has a budget of Php 200 and below, which is 34.67%, 53 of them has a budget of Php 201 – Php 300 representing the 35.33% of the size, 27 of them or 18% of the respondents has a budget of Php 301 – Php 400, 6 of them or 4% of the respondents has a budget of Php 401 – Php 500 and 12 respondents has a budget of Php 501 and above which is 2.67% of the size.

Table 7: Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Number of Times Visit

Number of Times Visit	Frequency	Percentage
Once a week	54	36.00%
2 – 3 times a week	75	50.00%
4 – 5 times a week	15	10.00%
6 – 7 times a week	6	4.00%
Average		100%

Table 7 out of 100 respondents shows the Number of Times Visit of each respondent. 54 of them visited Once a week, which is 36%, 28 of them visited 2 – 3 times a week representing the 50% of the size, 15 of them or 10% of the respondents visited 4 – 5 times a week, and 6 of them visited 6 – 7 times a week which is 4% of the respondents.

5. CONCLUSION

In Conclusion, the study on “Impacts of Green Practices to Customer Satisfaction Among Selected Coffee Shops in Dasmariñas City- Cavite” helps understand more about how green practices affect customer satisfaction. Green practices that are meticulously analyzed in terms of demographic profiles and customer perceptions reveal a striking correlation between enhanced levels of client satisfaction on the dimensions including quality, service prowess, and environmental sustainability. This research, therefore, highlights the critical role of coffee shops in bringing about positive environmental transformations while promoting customer engagement and loyalty. In addition, the analysis offers practical recommendations for coffee shop management, recommending adoption of superior guidelines including energy-efficient appliances use as well sustainable sourcing and waste management practices. Following these recommendations, coffee shops can not only differentiate themselves in competitive markets but also proactively participate in sustainable development global objectives. This study helps to provide directions in ongoing debates on evolving consumer behaviors, technological innovations and regulatory frameworks that are influencing sustainable business practices. In the end, by incorporating green practices into their operations coffee shops can build a culture of sustainability that creates a greener and more socially responsible future for both coffee industry in particular and society as whole.

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